

Smart And Effective Real Time Parking Management of Street Parking

Under the guidance of
Prof. Dr. Prasuna Vaddi
Dept. Electronics and communication
Atria Institute of Technology
Bangalore, India

Deepak M
Dept. Electronics and communication
Atria Institute of Technology
Bangalore, India

Deepika N
Dept. Electronics and communication
Atria Institute of Technology
Bangalore, India

Harshitha K S
Dept. Electronics and communication
Atria Institute of Technology
Bangalore, India

Kavitha G
Dept. Electronics and communication
Atria Institute of Technology
Bangalore, India

Abstract— This study proposes a holistic approach to urban parking management using smart technologies. It focuses on real-time parking slot availability monitoring, facilitated by smart sensors and data analytics, reducing congestion and frustration. Additionally, online booking systems streamline parking reservations, optimizing space utilization and improve convenience for drivers. Furthermore, advanced security measures, such as face recognition technology, are explored to combat car theft, enhancing vehicle security in parking areas. Through the integration of these smart solutions, we aim to create a more efficient, convenient, and secure urban parking experience, ultimately contributing to improved urban mobility and safety.

Keywords— Arduino uno, RFID Tag and reader, Node MCU, web camera, IR sensors.

I. INTRODUCTION

Smart street parking is a modern solution designed to optimize parking management in urban areas by utilizing innovative technologies. At its core, real-time management systems continuously monitor parking space occupancy, providing drivers with accurate information about available spots via mobile apps or electronic signage. This helps reduce traffic congestion and improves the overall parking experience. RFID tags and readers are integral components, enabling automated entry and exit processes without the need for physical tickets. Each vehicle is equipped with an RFID tag containing unique identification information, which is detected by readers installed at entry and exit points. This streamlined process enhances efficiency and reduces waiting times for drivers. Additionally, face recognition technology can be integrated to enhance security measures, identifying potential theft or unauthorized access in real-time. Surveillance cameras capture images of individuals accessing parking facilities, which are then compared against databases of known offenders or unauthorized users. If a match is found, alerts are sent to the authorities for prompt action. Smart street parking systems offer several benefits, including efficient space utilization, reduced traffic congestion, enhanced security, and improved user experience. By leveraging advanced technologies, these systems redefine urban mobility and pave the way for smarter, more sustainable cities.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The authors referenced in this overview [1, 2, 3, 4] offer a multifaceted exploration of smart street parking, delving into the integration of innovative technologies and the economic implications of energy production. Their collective research underscores the importance of real-time management systems and IR sensors in optimizing urban parking efficiency. Moreover, they shed light on the intricate relationship between energy costs, production structures, and the allocation of resources in the context of smart city infrastructure. Through their diverse perspectives and empirical analyses, these authors contribute significantly to the discourse on sustainable urban mobility and the future of transportation solutions.

IR Sensors in Smart Street Parking:

Innovations in smart street parking leverage IR sensors to optimize urban parking management. IR sensors detect the presence of vehicles in parking spaces, enabling real-time monitoring of occupancy and availability. Studies indicate that IR sensors play a crucial role in improving parking efficiency by providing accurate information to drivers, thereby reducing congestion and enhancing the overall parking experience [1]. Research also suggests that IR sensor technology contributes to cost-effective parking solutions, offering a reliable and scalable approach to urban parking management [2].

Real-Time Management in Smart Street Parking:

Real-time management systems are integral to smart street parking solutions, facilitating efficient utilization of parking spaces and enhancing traffic flow in urban areas. By continuously monitoring parking space occupancy and providing up-to-date information to drivers, real-time management systems optimize parking operations and reduce the time spent searching for parking [3]. Studies have shown that real-time management systems improve overall urban mobility by minimizing congestion and enhancing the user experience [4]. Furthermore, the implementation of real-time management systems is essential for cities seeking to address parking challenges and promote sustainable transportation solutions [5].

Online Booking Using Mobile Applications:

The integration of online booking systems via mobile applications revolutionizes the way drivers access and reserve parking spaces in smart street parking initiatives. Through mobile apps, drivers can conveniently search for available parking spots, reserve them in advance, and seamlessly navigate to their designated spaces upon arrival [6]. Research highlights the benefits of online booking systems, including improved convenience, reduced search time, and enhanced user satisfaction [7]. Moreover, online booking systems contribute to efficient parking space utilization and can help cities better manage parking demand in high-traffic areas [8].

Number Plate Recognition in Smart Street Parking:

Number plate recognition technology is a key component of smart street parking systems, enabling automated vehicle identification and access control. By capturing and processing vehicle number plates, this technology streamlines the entry and exit process, eliminating the need for physical tickets or manual checks [9]. Studies suggest that number plate recognition systems enhance security, deter theft, and improve overall parking efficiency [10]. Additionally, the integration of number plate recognition technology offers cities valuable data insights for parking management and enforcement purposes [11].

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The prevailing sentiment across numerous papers underscores continuous monitoring is crucial to ensure environmental safety, while also highlighting the limitations of manual monitoring methods. One such paper introduces a sensor-based monitoring system renowned for its attributes data collection, and mobility. It accentuates the critical importance of real-time data access and notifications in ensuring timely responses to environmental threats. Furthermore, it advocates for the adoption of cloud-based Internet of Things (IoT) systems for real-time traffic monitoring and control, addressing the inefficiencies and time wastage associated with traditional methods.

Detailed review emphasizes importance of IoT-based systems and sensor networks and IoT technology in facilitating efficient management and real-time monitoring. By leveraging these technologies, users can effectively monitor environmental conditions and traffic patterns, leading to enhanced safety and operational efficiency.

- Acknowledging the shortcomings of manual monitoring procedures and the requirement for automated, ongoing monitoring solutions

IV. PROBLEM STATEMENT

- There is a lot of wastage of resources while waiting for parking in urban cities. Due to waiting, it can lead to traffic congestion which will result in air pollution. Specially with areas of poor air quality index this is a serious problem.
- There is a tremendous increase in the use of vehicles. Going offices, home etc is a routine activity and people find it difficult to park their vehicles efficiently and there is wastage of time. So, a smart parking system that will help users to check about empty slots has been proposed.

V. AIM AND OBJECTIVE

Our project aims to implement an IoT-based smart and efficient real-time street parking maintenance ecosystem to enhance maintainability. The objectives include real-time monitoring, which involves continuously collecting data through sensors and storing it in the cloud. Low-cost sensors are utilized to monitor available and unavailable parking spots, with the goal of optimizing parking by assisting users in finding the best spot, thereby saving time, resources, and effort. Additionally, the system ensures that parking lots are efficiently filled and properly utilized by commercial entities. By addressing parking emissions, which currently burn approximately one million barrels of oil per day, significant reductions can be achieved. This improves the efficiency of parking management but also contributes to environmental sustainability.

VI. METHODOLOGY

- Research and Planning: Identify project requirements and objectives through thorough research and assessment of existing smart parking systems.
- Design and Development: Plan system architecture and integration, developing detailed installation and configuration plans.
- Installation: Install IR sensors, RFID readers, and face recognition cameras with proper alignment and connectivity for accurate monitoring.
- Integration with Telegram: Develop a user-friendly Telegram interface and integrate it with the central parking management system.
- Testing and Optimization: Conduct comprehensive testing to ensure functionality and reliability, optimizing system performance and user experience.
- Deployment and Monitoring: Deploy the system in the target area and monitor its performance and user feedback post-deployment.
- Training and Maintenance: Provide stakeholders with training on system usage and establish protocols for ongoing maintenance and support.

VII. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Working

The objective is to develop a low-power, low-cost, high-accuracy wireless sensor network system for continuous parking monitoring at remote places. Parking spaces can be monitored using sensors is the key to smart and effective real-time management of street parking. Using wireless technology, it can transmit data to processing system. Viewing parking availability, reserving spots, and receiving notification are all possible through a mobile app or website. Automated enforcement mechanisms, like ticketing for overstaying, improve parking turnover. Integrating with city infrastructure enables dynamic pricing and traffic flow management, improving efficiency and user experience. Communication Interface plays a major role in automation and process monitoring.

The data is shown on the LCD display. The received data is transmitted to the Telegram. The gained findings is sent to the smartphone.

Fig.1 smart parking

IR Sensors for Vehicle Sensing:

IR sensors are installed in every parking space to detect the presence of vehicles, ensuring accurate monitoring of occupancy. The data collected by these sensors is transmitted in real-time to a central system, enabling efficient management of parking availability.

RFID Tag and Readers for Booking and Gate Control:

Vehicles are equipped with RFID tags that contain unique identification information. RFID readers are installed at both entry and exit points of the parking facility. When a vehicle approaches the entry point, the RFID reader scans the tag to retrieve the vehicle's booking details from the central database. If the booking is confirmed, the gate opens automatically, granting the vehicle entry into the parking area. This streamlined process ensures efficient access control and enhances the user experience for drivers

DC Motor: The DC motor controls the barrier gate at the entry/exit point of the parking area. It receives commands from the microcontroller to open or close the gate based on the availability of parking spaces or the validity of RFID tags.

Fig. 2 Block diagram

Integration with Telegram for Timings and Amount Details:

A Telegram bot or interface is developed to provide users with a convenient platform to interact with the parking system. Through this interface, users can easily check the availability of parking slots, make bookings, and receive confirmation messages in real-time. Additionally, Telegram displays detailed information regarding the timings and associated amount for the slots that have been booked, enabling users to plan their parking effectively.

DC Motor: The DC motor controls the barrier gate at the entry/exit point of the parking area. It receives commands from the microcontroller to open or close the gate based on the availability of parking spaces or the validity of RFID tags.

Cameras for Face Recognition:

- Install cameras equipped with face recognition software at entry and exit points.
- These cameras capture images of individuals accessing the parking area and analyze them for facial recognition.

Integration with Telegram for Face Recognition:

The integration of Telegram with face recognition technology enhances security in the parking system. If a parked person's face does not match at the exit gate, the system captures the face and sends it to the booked person through Telegram. Upon receiving the notification, the booked person can choose to accept or reject the face match. If accepted, the exit gate opens; otherwise, it remains closed, ensuring that only authorized individuals can exit the parking area.

VIII. RESULT

- Our project Smart Street Parking aims to automate and decrease the time spent searching for parking spots.
- It involves the use of low-cost sensors, real-time data, and applications for monitoring available and unavailable spots.
- The goal is to optimize parking by helping users find the best spot, saving time, resources, and effort.
- It can help reduce traffic as fewer cars are required to drive around in search of an open spot.
- Face recognition cameras can gather footage for security purposes.
- Implementing a smart parking solution can help decrease management costs by automating processes.
- This includes driver's payment, spot identification, location search, and time notifications.

IX. REQUIREMENTS

Hardware

- Node MCU ESP8266: The processing board, containing the ESP8266 Wi-Fi module, 30 pins including digital, analog, VCC, GND, GPIO, and USB ports, a reset button, and a flash button.
- Sensors :IR Sensor RFID Tag reader.
- Micro USB cable: for powering the Node MCU board.
- DC Motor: Rotatory device allows control of angular as well as linear motion

Software

- Arduino IDE: Integrated Development Environment for programming the Node MCU board.

X. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the integration of RFID technology and face recognition in smart street parking systems marks a significant leap forward in urban parking management. These technologies streamline access, enhance security, and improve efficiency, ultimately contributing to smoother traffic flow and a better parking experience for users. By leveraging advanced features such as personalized services and real-time monitoring, these systems lay the foundation for smarter and more sustainable cities of the future. As urban populations continue to grow, embracing innovative solutions like RFID and face recognition in parking management will be crucial for optimizing urban spaces and improving quality of life for residents and visitors alike.

XI. REFERENCES

- [1]. Gupta, A., & Kumar, N. (2018). Smart parking system using IoT. In 2018 3rd International Conference for Convergence in Technology (I2CT) (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- [2]. Song, Y., Yu, J., Zeng, P., & Luo, J. (2018). Design and Implementation of IoT-based Intelligent Parking Management System. In 2018 International Conference on Computer, Information and Telecommunication Systems (CITS) (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- [3]. Tazil, M., & Wahid, K. (2018). A smart parking system using IoT. In 2018 International Conference on Computing, Engineering, and Design (ICCED) (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- [4]. Gupta, R., & Dahiya, V. (2019). Smart parking system using IoT. In 2019 3rd International Conference on Trends in Electronics and Informatics (ICOEI) (pp. 846-850). IEEE.
- [5]. Javed, M. A., Javaid, N., Khan, M. A., & Khan, Z. A. (2019). Design and implementation of IoT-based smart parking system using MQTT protocol. In 2019 4th International Conference on Computing, Mathematics and Engineering Technologies (iCoMET) (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- [6]. Kallappa, K., & Desai, C. (2019). Smart parking system using IoT. In 2019 4th International Conference on Internet of Things: Smart Innovation and Usages (IoT-SIU) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [7]. Sarkar, A., Kar, S., & Sarkar, R. (2019). Design and implementation of an IoT-based smart parking system using Raspberry Pi. In 2019 2nd International Conference on Advanced Computational and Communication Paradigms (ICACCP) (pp. 1-5). IEEE.

- [8]. Yang, Y., Wang, Y., & Chen, S. (2019). Design and implementation of smart parking system based on Internet of Things. In 2019 International Conference on Internet of Things (iThings) and IEEE Green Computing and Communications (GreenCom) and IEEE Cyber, Physical and Social Computing (CPSCom) and IEEE Smart Data (SmartData) (pp. 1850-1853). IEEE.
- [9]. Al-Fuqaha, A., Guizani, M., Mohammadi, M., Aledhari, M., & Ayyash, M. (2015). Internet of things: A survey on enabling technologies, protocols, and applications. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 17(4), 2347-2376.
- [10]. Hwang, H. (2020). Design and implementation of a smart parking system using IoT-based sensor networks. In 2020 International Conference on Information Networking (ICOIN) (pp. 327-330). IEEE.
- [11]. Kim, D., & Kim, S. (2020). Smart parking management system based on IoT technology. In 2020 International Conference on Information Networking (ICOIN) (pp. 321-326). IEEE.
- [12]. Nirmal, A., & Prabha, G. (2021). IoT-based smart parking system using Raspberry Pi. In 2021 International Conference on Advanced Informatics for Computing Research (ICAICR) (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- [13]. Shahid, S., Imran, M., & Ahn, S. (2022). An IoT-based smart parking management system using LoRaWAN. In 2022 International Conference on Electronics, Information, and Communication (ICEIC) (pp. 1-5). IEEE.